

Enhanced Smart Advertising through Federated Learning

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Abstract—Smart advertising is growing in popularity and affecting businesses. Smart advertising is a more friendly, interactive, personalised, and creative method of promoting a product, and attempts to delight clients. AROUND is a social networking service that emphasizes smart advertising through an effective recommender system. The system considers user profiles, history, social network connections, mood, and IoT-supported positioning to select the most relevant ads using machine learning technology. Although the current deployment of the AROUND system is based on the cloud, an edge-based architecture provides relevant improvement in terms of system response time. In this paper we extend the edge-based strategy to leverage the potential of federated learning on multiple distributed edge servers. We show that federated learning can take advantage of the distributed nature of the system, and leverage the specificities of local features. In fact, in this research, we propose a novel federated learning solution to provide smart advertising as a classification problem which uses ensemble methods and logistic regression as internal (local) models and meta-heuristic algorithms for federated learning aggregation. As part of the experiments, we prove this technology on a real data set with more than one million registers, and show the efficiency in terms of enhanced accuracy and improved training and response speed.

I. INTRODUCTION

Smart cities employ information and communication technologies to enhance quality of life for citizens and promote environmental and social sustainability [1]. Such cities make it easier for people to communicate and share information, which helps businesses to be more efficient and able to adapt quickly to changes in the market.

Consumers are now immersed in a vast and complex array of networks made up of an interconnected mesh of people, businesses, and, more recently, objects thanks to the development of the Internet of Things (IoT). This connectivity is enhanced by mobile devices, which facilitates a variety of interactions in these networks. Numerous smart city innovative urban services are taking advantage of these advances in technology, for example, intelligent transportation systems, smart healthcare, environment monitoring at real-time, sophisticated smart home solutions, energy and public safety, and many more that are evolving every day.

Smart advertising is one area where smart services are rising in popularity and, more importantly, in commercial impact. Smart advertising is advertising with intelligence that aims to create exceptional and personalized experiences for customers. As opposed to traditional advertising, smart advertising raises

awareness of a product using a more friendly, interactive, creative, and customized approach. The digital advertising industry is one of the fastest-growing industries globally, with mobile advertising making up a significant proportion of open-source digital advertising. In fact, mobile advertising accounts for 51% of the entire digital market, as reported by Grewal et al. [2].

The social network AROUND, which serves small and medium-sized businesses, is a member of a larger family of intelligent advertising platforms [3]. This application's main approach, with over 3 million users, is smart advertising with the help of IoT positioning sensors. Multiple Bluetooth low-energy beacons are deployed in various locations throughout commercial shopping malls in order to track customers and provide advertisers with personalised interactive functionality. The AROUND system is based on a smart recommender system that recommends appealing businesses and friends to each user based on their profile, history, current mood, time spent at a location such as a shop, and current location.

This application's current working implementation is cloud-based. Positioning data from beacons is sent to the cloud via users' smartphone apps, and combined with users' profiles and advertising campaigns for personalized feedback using advanced ML technologies. As more users are detected in beacon range areas, the data and personalized requests also increase, leading to longer processing times in the cloud and potentially reducing user satisfaction.

Edge computing extends the traditional cloud computing model by leveraging compute resources closer to customers and end devices in order to reduce latency. Edge computing is commonly feasible solely at servers situated within close proximity to end devices, typically at macro or micro base stations, within one or a few hops [4]. In a recent research work [5], a new edge-based architecture was proposed for the AROUND system to leverage the edge computing capabilities. In such proposal, the recommender computation was offloaded to different servers at the edge, closer to the customers, thus reducing the long communications latency and drastically improving the response time. Surprisingly, we realized that the response time was reduced not only by the communications distance reduction, but also because the local ML processes were simpler (only considered the local data subset) and because all registers exposed a higher locality in the training

model.

As part of ML, Federated Learning (FL), or collaborative learning, is a way to train a ML algorithm on multiple decentralized edge servers that store local data records without sharing them with other devices or servers. Federated Learning (FL) facilitates the collaborative development of a machine learning model by multiple actors, without necessitating the sharing of data. This stands in contrast to conventional machine learning methods, which rely on the aggregation of all local data records onto a single server, as well as other decentralised approaches that frequently presume uniform distribution of data samples. FL enables the exploitation of locality-specific characteristics and facilitates the resolution of significant concerns such as safeguarding data privacy and security, managing data access rights, ensuring efficient access to diverse data, and enhancing the precision and resilience of learning models.

In this paper, we improve the edge-based strategy for the AROUND recommender component in order to take advantage of the distributed system architecture and the FL paradigm. The edge-based architecture not only provides a fast response time for recommendations but also maintains data local, allowing the exploitation of local specific features through the FL models as well as increasing data privacy and security. The new recommender system improves overall system performance and improves the quality and accuracy of the smart advertising system by taking into account locality specificities. Real historic data from the AROUND system database (a cross section of 1 Million users behavior) has been used for analysing different scenarios. We have compared the accuracy of the edge-based approach with respect to the cloud strategy and show a noticeable improvement of model performance and training time.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. In section II a literature review of related works is presented. The AROUND system is described in Section III, together with the edge-based model. In Section IV different solutions to adopt a Federated Learning model are discussed. Section V presents the experimental analysis that confirms the effectiveness of the proposed strategy. The paper concludes in Section VI, summarizing the main research findings.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

The term "mobile advertising" was coined at the beginning of this century and refers to advertising through mobile devices, such as smartphones. Mobile advertising is described as the use of wireless media to assist stakeholders by recognizing their needs and offering relevant product and service information [2]. Extensive literature has been produced around mobile advertising, most of which base their strategy on tracking location-based private data in mobile ad networks [6]. Geolocation significantly impacts targeted ad tracking behavior, and raises security concerns for ad organizations aggregating private user data across multiple apps.

As an enhancement of mobile advertising, the term "smart advertising" includes more sophisticated methods for per-

sonalized recommendation, often requiring the combination of sophisticated technology, such as IoT devices as well as complex data analysis technologies. In this context, some literature can be found addressing different aspects of this problem.

For instance, Lee et al. [7] designed a high-level operational framework to provide more diverse marketing strategies based on location-based plot placement 2D animation. Utilising user experience theories, marketing plans for personalised plot placement and geo-information technologies are proposed and evaluated.

In Li and Xu [8], the authors noticed that users receive ads from homogeneous categories based on their utility scores. For this reason, they proposed a diversity-aware mobile framework which shows diverse ads. This was designed as a multichoice knapsack problem, using greedy and genetic algorithms to solve it, and locating users through GPS.

More recently, Viktoratos and Tsadiras [9] focus their research in exploring the cold-start problem in personalized mobile advertisement systems, proposing a novel prediction approach when users have limited or no data available in the recommender system. A variety of machine learning techniques have been tested, including logistic regression, support vector machines, and even deep learning techniques like FLEN and DeepFM.

Other algorithms, including support vector machine, random forest, and artificial neural networks, have been studied for artificially enabled location-based services for mobile advertising [10]. They built an effective visualization of geographic areas with the relevance score for a fixed set of categories.

All of these works paved the way for contemporary smart advertising and presented smart advertising prototypes; however, a method with improved efficacy, acceptable time complexity, and a high degree of personalization at the user level appears to be required.

III. BACKGROUND

In this section we first present the AROUND application and describe the proposed edge-based system strategy for increased performance. Then, we review some basic concepts on distributed ML that are important to understand the proposed learning architecture.

A. The AROUND application

The AROUND application is a social networking platform that utilizes an intelligent advertising system to specifically cater to small and medium-sized businesses. AROUND's goal is to connect customers and businesses by creating personalized ads in order to provide an optimized shopping experience and increase potential business between both sides [3]. The AROUND system has been installed with 12,000 beacons in Iran and Russia, and it boasts a user base of over 3 million individuals, with one million of them being active users.

AROUND system classifies users as traders (businesses) or customers, with traders collaborating to offer personalized advertising based on user profiles. AROUND deploys over

3,000 beacons in Tehran to facilitate localized interactions with customers, benefitting over 800 registered traders, as shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Map of current beacon deployment in the city of Tehran.

Customers are users of the app who seek social networking, exchange experiences, and personalized shopping. Upon registration, customers create their profile, and they are presented with five mood options daily, as displayed in Fig. 2.a. The primary offering extended to users of AROUND pertains to the provision of personalised advertising recommendations based on their past behaviour. This is accomplished through an analysis of their in-app activity and present geographic location, which is then integrated with their current emotional state. As an example, Fig. 2.b shows an advertisement sample.

Fig. 2. Screenshot of the mood selection (a) and sample advertisement (b) in AROUND.

Fig. 3 shows how the AROUND system is currently operating. Beacons are set up in places where businesses have registered, like stores and museums. The app on a registered customer’s smartphone detects the beacon when they approach the store (1) and establishes a connection with the cloud-based AROUND server (2). The server runs the trained model and chooses the best advertisement for the customer based on the profile and the location of the customer (as determined by the device location and beacon status) (3-4-5). The customer receives a reply along with access to the personalised offers and discounts via their smartphone app (6).

Each time a user is detected by a beacon, a request is dispatched to a docker instance in a Kubernetes orchestration

Fig. 3. Basic operation of the AROUND system.

system as part of the decision process [11]. AROUND system clusters user requests into 9 categories using a model that considers user behavior, age, past activity, and interaction history to suggest the best category based on their current mood. It then decides on a personalized advertisement for the user. The system is currently centralized in the cloud.

B. An edge-based strategy

The AROUND system uses an edge-based approach where the recommender is moved to the edge for immediate response, while global and strategic tasks are kept in the cloud. Businesses located in close proximity often collaborate to utilise shared computing resources, thereby managing a smaller subset of localised advertising campaigns and customer data. The initial synchronisation of a customer’s data in a novel region is not a prerequisite for enrollment. Once the customer’s smartphone is within the range of a registered beacon, the intelligent recommendation process is initiated locally on a nearby server, as shown in Fig. 4. The reduced latency resulting from the server’s proximity leads to a significant decrease in the duration between the submission of the request and the receipt of the customised promotional material.

Fig. 4. Edge-based strategy for the AROUND system.

Advantages of the strategy include reduced latency and communication time due to local execution, decreased risk of system overload in a smaller area, lower complexity of the

recommendation process from a smaller dataset, and reduced security risks through local storage and processing.

Despite the initial appearance of high expenses, the deployment costs can be counterbalanced by an expanding community of contented system users.

C. Distributed and Federated ML

As the amount of available data continues to grow, the use of automatic data analysis tools becomes increasingly important. However, traditional learning algorithms face challenges in processing vast amounts of data in a reasonable timeframe. To overcome this limitation, large-scale learning has emerged as a new trend in machine learning.

Distributed learning is a promising approach to scaling up learning algorithms by allocating the process across multiple workstations [12].

Distributed learning can be addressed in two different approaches, depending on how the data is organized. The classical concept of distributed learning is related to a scenario where data are evenly distributed among nodes, and a global learning process is executed in parallel. Alternatively, a different scenario is when data sets are naturally spread, for instance, a network of hospitals where each hospital generates and manages its own data registers privately. In this scenario, both efficiency and security are improved by executing locally their own learning processes and, then, combining the learning models among the federation of hospitals. This method is known as Federated Learning (FL), and it deals with naturally distributed data sets, a common occurrence in many real-world scenarios [13]. FL is the joint training of machine learning models using distributed devices and local data under federation. It enables effective training of machine learning models while preserving data privacy and legal compliance of the participants.

Ensemble learning with multiple classifiers trained on distributed data sets can improve accuracy, particularly for large domains. Combining different classifiers can integrate their learning biases and compensate for their inefficiencies [14]. Ensemble learning combines multiple classifiers to improve accuracy. Popular methods involve training classifiers on different subsets of data and then combining them through an ensemble strategy. This approach is well-suited to distributed environments, where each site can train a classifier on its own subset of data before aggregating them.

IV. FEDERATED SMART ADVERTISING IN AROUND

In this section, we first present the current recommender system of AROUND and its limitation. Then we present the details of the new solution with the help of edge computing and FL.

A. The current recommender system

In the current recommender system users are labeled through a main clustering algorithm with a customized distance function by an R-Plumber API which is deployed on the main cloud server. Each of ten different clusters receive

different types of advertisements and suggestions, and it is believed these behaviors are the core difference of users' responses to our promotions and campaigns.

When a large number of users move from a socioeconomic zone to another it results in a misclassification, because their main last location plays an important role in the classification of users. In order to solve this limitation, additional information should be considered to enhance the users' classification and fine tune the model.

This will be addressed by taking advantage of the locality features in FL so that edge nodes are further classified according to the socioeconomic level at their zone. This additional model parameter will provide more accurate recommendations at each specific area by leveraging local common features, while facilitating a global integration in the federation, as described in the next subsection.

B. The federated recommender system

The FL system will be trained at two different levels. First, an edge side level, where each edge node has its own local model considering the specific behavior details of their users, which is described by the different coefficients of their significant variables which stays in the model. And second, a central side level model at the cloud which should be trained by the gathered data for estimation of the additive part of the multinomial model which represents the random effects for multilevel models.

Considerations are needed when moving data from the edge to the cloud. Data can be anonymized or wiped after use for successful model convergence. The key concern is ensuring models on different edges are performing well and meeting an accuracy threshold.

The architecture of the FL method used in this work is now described. The model selected as the internal (local) model in FL is the logistic regression model. In the pre-processing phase, an outlier detection with Cook's Distance and COF is performed. Then for feature selection a Random Forest ensemble model is developed to obtain the relative feature importance.

After these initial activities, the main part of the federated learning process, which is the aggregation of local results, is performed with the help of meta-heuristic algorithms. WOA, BA, and FA algorithms are candidate algorithms for this purpose that are tested and compared in this work to find the best one.

We aim to find the optimal aggregation settings for local models using meta-heuristic methods. This involves testing different weight arrays to determine the best one. After multiple iterations, the optimal setting will be selected for the final aggregation process.

The fitness function for comparing weighted arrays in the aggregation process is the maximum prediction error, which is minimized through iterations of a meta-heuristic method. This results in the best option for the final forecast. A high convergence optimization method is needed for efficient operation, hence the selection of the three algorithms with fast

convergence. The best algorithm is determined through testing and comparison in the results section.

V. RESULTS

Real data from the AROUND system was analyzed to evaluate the effectiveness of the FL approach. Semi-unbalanced labeled data with one million registers was used for training. PQL method with Laplace approximation was used for estimating random effects and standard error, while Maximum Likelihood was used for estimating fixed effects. The label was changed to make user activity more visible, with the model converging after 6 to 7 iterations using iterative algorithms.

To implement the proposed method and evaluate it, we first need to select meta-heuristic algorithm and some other parameters. So, an initial test on meta-heuristic candidates done that shows the WOA has fastest convergence in our architecture and we used this algorithm to obtain our results.

After selecting WOA as the best algorithm for meta-heuristics aggregation, the following configuration will be used for further experiments:

- Logistic regression for local models
- 120 federated learning iterations
- WOA for aggregation, with population size 50 and 10 WOA iterations (very fast in convergence)

Fig. 5. Impact of proposed federated aggregation on model performance (Nagel Kerke).

Fig. 6. Impact of proposed federated aggregation on model performance (coefficient of determination).

Number of new users	Centralized cloud	Edge based model
100	29.382930	28.665000
200	30.383856	29.458000
500	60.369138	58.923000
1000	118.923760	73.107000
5000	908.731933	289.418700
10000	2184.516667	419.327900
15000	3009.214006	753.246100

TABLE I

TRAINING TIME IN SCENARIOS FOR 7 LEVELS OF NUMBER OF USERS

A. Model accuracy

The aim of this experiment is to evaluate model performance and accuracy using three statistical criteria: R-square, Fisher Ratio, and Nagel Kerke, to demonstrate their accuracy.

Figures 5 and 6 show the histogram of the models in terms of prediction accuracy using the proposed aggregation and without using it on different classes (5 with Nagel Kerke as metric and 6 with Coefficient of Determination as metric). The comparison of the two figures shows that the use of the proposed aggregation method in most classes has led to much higher accuracy. For example, the coefficient of determination for classes 1 and 9 has exceeded 0.98 and an almost perfect mode has been obtained for these two classes. In some classes, such as class 5, where this number is equal to 0.91, although less accuracy has been improved, it is still better than the default aggregation.

B. Training speed

To assess the learning process time, two modes, centralized and edge-based, were examined for different numbers of users. The results for this step are the worst cases (Maximum Time) for 7 levels of users count that is displayed in Table I and also in Figure 7 visually. These results show that in the edge-based mode, the growth of learning time is less with the increase of the number of users. For example, with an increase in the number of users between 100 and 1000, the growth of learning time in the centralized cloud is more than 4 times, while this number is about 2.5 times for the edge-based mode. Therefore, increasing the number of users in the edge-based system has less time overhead.

Fig. 7. Training time comparison on increasing number of users.

C. Response speed

We used a multinomial logit model on a Raspberry Pi 4 in a centralized cloud to calculate response speed. We tested three edge-to-central cloud user ratios and found that edge servers require at least a four-core CPU for more than 200 users without a central cloud. The response time includes the time to compute a user's class, transmit their data, and return their class. These results are displayed on Figure 8.

Fig. 8. Response speed comparison

In Figure 8, the response times have been calculated for the case in which all users are in the same edge node. This means that the maximum possible response time has been calculated. According to this fact, for example for 500 users the response time is 2.95 in the worst case and in the actual environment this is much better than the time in this table.

In summary, using an edge-based environment with federated learning and the proposed aggregation mechanism has significantly improved the accuracy and generality of the learning process. Additionally, selecting an optimisation algorithm with higher convergence has improved the learning speed and response time.

VI. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this paper has proposed a federated learning strategy to improve the effectiveness and efficiency of the AROUND recommender system. Through the use of an edge-based architecture and random effect parameters in the main cloud, our model has achieved higher accuracy and reduced response time. The proposed method has resulted in an improvement of nearly 9% in the coefficient of determination (R^2) and a reduction in response time by over 30%. Different sample sizes have confirmed the accuracy of the models in the average mode. Our findings indicate that the implementation of our proposed federated learning approach can significantly enhance the performance of recommender systems in the digital advertising industry. Further research could explore the use of federated learning in other areas of the industry and investigate the scalability of the proposed method for larger datasets.

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